

SCIENTIFIC AND THEORETICAL BASIS OF DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' INFORMATION COMPETENCE USING DIGITAL EDUCATIONAL TECHNOLOGIES

Karimova Nilufar Boltaboyevna

Independent researcher of Urgench State University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.10802739>

Abstract: This thesis discusses the scientific-theoretical features of using digital educational technologies in the development of students' information competence during higher education.

Key words: Educational system, digital educational technologies, information competence, professional conditions.

INTRODUCTION

The evolution of society is inextricably linked with the development of education: it is in this sphere that the social, psychological, general cultural and professional conditions of social development lie. The concept of the new social order is significantly different from the previous one due to the production and wide distribution of information in all spheres of human life based on digitalization, providing wide access to information sources, and the high level of automation of information processing in production and social spheres. Under such conditions, a rational understanding of the world is crucial in the search for the most optimal ways of development of modern civilization. Digital educational technologies accompanying the formation of a new society led to an increase in the scope of cognitive activity, the transfer of knowledge production to an information-technological basis, and the wide use of information technologies as a means of obtaining new knowledge.

A modern teacher should not only have the amount of knowledge necessary for professional activity, but also creatively use it in educational activities:

- determining the goals of cognitive activity;
- find optimal ways to achieve goals;
- use of various information sources;
- searching and finding the necessary information, evaluating the obtained results;
- organization of one's activity;
- cooperation with students.

It is impossible to become a qualified specialist without paying attention to the spectrum of modern innovative digital education technologies, ideas, directions and approaches implemented in the field of education today. We talk

about activity, competence, person-oriented, systematic, technological and other approaches. In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the concept of "approach" is considered as a set of techniques, methods (in influencing someone, learning something, doing business). Usually, the analysis of the "approach" category is considered in special periods of the development of a certain activity, in particular, in education, when radical changes are noted or when problems arise that cannot be solved by existing means. The educational process, according to G. K. Selevko, requires the use of certain methodological approaches, because the approach itself exists as a clear emphasis of the entire complex of activity content, methods, tools and mechanisms used in the pedagogical process.

The analysis of the extensive and rich materials of the advanced pedagogical experience of educational innovations allows us to see the conceptual basis, structural features and methods used in each modern approach, and the existence of the material necessary to understand the essence of the educational development process. For example, in the framework of the activity approach, in a simplified sense, activity teaching is carried out, which implies the implementation of joint educational and cognitive activities of a group of students under the guidance of a teacher at the first stage of education. In addition, the main task of the student is to complete assignments independently with the corrective help of the teacher.

The digital technological approach in education provides instrumental management of the educational process to achieve the specified educational goals. This approach allows more accurate prediction of educational results and management of pedagogical processes.

Systemic approach (I. B. Novikov, Z. A. Reshetova, A. Ya. Fridland, etc.) allows to see all elements of the educational process in an interrelated structure - a system of interrelated structural elements. Systematic action involves determining the goals of the educational system, separating its connections with other systems.

The modern stage of educational development is characterized by an increasingly dense introduction of the competence-based approach, which needs a more detailed description in the context of our research, which implies a clear direction to the future, which takes into account the success of each person in his professional and personal activities. It is manifested in the ability to build education, as well as the ability to make a choice based on an appropriate assessment of one's own capabilities. According to E. F. Zeer, the competency-based approach is a priority focus on educational goals: learning, self-awareness,

self-determination, socialization, and development of individuality. The theoretical development of the foundations of the competency-based approach of domestic and foreign pedagogical sciences began in the 60s of the 20th century. Studying the history of the development of this direction on the basis of the materials of psychological and pedagogical literature allows to observe its evolution. Thus, I. A. Zimnaya distinguished three stages in the development of the theory of competence-based approach, gave a brief description of each of them based on an in-depth analysis of the works of scientists.

At this stage of the development of the competence-based approach, Professor L. M. Mitina introduced the concept of "pedagogical competence", which includes "knowledge, skills, as well as methods and methods of their implementation in activities, communication, personal development (self-development)".

At this stage of the genesis of the competence-based approach, new competences, including information, are allocated. The authors describe specific competencies and capabilities that can be successfully applied in the field of education.

In the early 2000s, a new stage began in the development of the theory and practice of the competency-based approach in education. In 2004, G. K. Selevko, a leading Russian theoretical teacher, the author of the technological approach in education, stated that the traditional approach, in which the goals of education are determined by the set of knowledge and skills that the student must acquire, is not enough to form a professionally qualified specialist. According to the author, the competency-based approach is "a step-by-step reorientation of the dominant educational paradigm with a preferential translation of knowledge, the formation of skills, modern multi-digital educational technologies, socio-political, market-economic, means creating conditions for mastering a set of competencies that represent the potential and ability of a graduate for survival and sustainable life in the conditions of an information and communication saturated space.

According to A. G. Bermus, Doctor of Pedagogical Sciences, the prototype of modern ideas about the competence-based approach is the ideas of general and personal development, formed in the context of psychological and pedagogical concepts of person-oriented and developing education. In this regard, competences are considered as "end-to-end, over- and meta-subject formations that combine both traditional knowledge and various generalized intellectual, creative, worldview, methodological, communicative and other skills." Thus, the competence-based approach prioritizes not the acquisition of information, but

the ability to solve problems that arise in various, including new professional and pedagogical situations.

Currently, the competency-based approach to the education system continues to be introduced. As stated in the project of concepts for the development of education, it is envisaged to solve a number of priority tasks in order to realize the main goal of the concept - to increase the access to quality education. One of these tasks is to provide educational services, including the expansion of the use of modern educational and information technologies, to ensure the expansion of competencies acquired by students while maintaining the study period. According to Y. I. Kuzminova, the new educational paradigm will be successful only if it is directed to the formation of the needs for continuous replenishment and updating of knowledge, improvement of skills and qualifications, their integration and transformation into competences.

Thus, the competence-based approach is based on the following position: during the educational process, a person must acquire knowledge oriented to specific practice and develop certain important social and professional qualities, as a result of which he can be successful in life.

The transformation of education into a high-tech field involves pedagogical research and the development of problems related to the formation of information competence of future specialists, including students. Education received at a higher educational institution, focused on practical skills, the ability to apply knowledge in new pedagogical conditions and situations, plays a special role in the formation of an information competent teacher. In this approach, general professional subjects aimed at mastering digital educational technologies by students are important. In particular, the use of digital educational technologies in the educational process increases the professional opportunities of students, especially the pedagogical culture should include such professional knowledge, skills, knowledge and activity experience, which together are called "information competence".

In the context of our research, the leading categories are "competence", "information competence", "professional competence". Despite the fact that these terms are actively used in scientific and educational literature, in normative and everyday speech dictionaries, the interpretation of the concepts behind them still remains unclear. Before defining the term "information competence" as the key to our research, it is necessary to define the concepts and the main approaches available to them - "*competence*".

References:

1. Bilotta, E., Bertacchini, F., Gabriele, L., Giglio, S., Pantano, P. S., & Romita, T. (2021) turizm ta'limida sanoat 4.0 texnologiyalari: talabalarni texnologiya bilan fikrlashga o'rgatish. Mehmondo'stlik, bo'sh vaqt, Sport va turizm ta'limi jurnali, 29.
2. Dudar, V. L., Riznik, V. V., Kotsur, V. V., Pechenizka, S. S. Va Kovtun, O. A. (2021). Masofaviy va aralash ta'lim sharoitida modern texnologiyalari va raqamli vositalardan foydalanish. Tilshunoslik va Madaniyat sharhi, 5 (S2) (2021) 733-750. <https://doi.org/10.21744/lingcure.v5nS2.1416>
3. Ugli, S. S. O. R. T. (2023). Theoretical principles of preparing future teachers for the professional-pedagogical activity directed to the socialization of students on the base of a gender approach. International Multidisciplinary Journal for Research & Development, 10(11), 162-166.
4. Sharifzoda, S., & Karimov, K. (2024). Theoretical principles of developing socio-cultural competence of graduate students on the base of gender approach. Академические исследования в современной науке, 3(5), 5-9.
5. Sharifzoda, S., & Karimov, H. (2024). Bitiruvchi sinf o'quvchilarining o'quv faoliyatini rag'batlantirishning gender xususiyatlari. Молодые ученые, 2(4), 4-7.
6. Sharifzoda, S. O. Texnologiya ta'limi jarayonida integrativ texnologiyalar foydalanib o'quvchilarda tayanch kompetensiyalarni shakllantirish imkoniyatlari. Международный научно-образовательный электронный журнал «Образование и наука в XXI веке», (16), 172-178.
7. M., Beardsley Albó, L. P., & Hernández-Leo, D. (2021) o'qituvchi qobiliyat va motivatsiya bo'yicha Favqulodda ta'lim ta'sir raqamli texnologiyalardan foydalanish Aragón. Britaniya ta'lim texnologiyalari jurnali, 52 (4), 1455-1477.
8. Шарифзода, С. Ў. Т. Ўқувчиларда таянч компетенцияларни шакллантириш асосида ижтимоий компетентлиликни таркиб топтириш мазмуни.
9. Сардорбек, Ш. (2023). Gender pedagogikasining dolzarb muammolari. научно-теоретический журнал "ma'mun science", 1(1).
10. Sharifzoda, S. O. (2021). Ўқувчиларда таянч компетенцияларни шакллантириш асосида ижтимоий компетентлиликни таркиб топтириш мазмуни. Academic research in educational sciences, 2(6), 2181-1385.